

Mesoporous TiO₂-CeO₂ composites for photocatalytic CO₂ reduction

Mateja Knap^{1,2}, Urška Lavrenčič Štangar², Andrijana Sever Škapin^{1,3}, Miroslava Filip Edelmannová⁴, Kamila Kočí⁴, Peter Nadrah^{1,*}

¹ Slovenian National Building and Civil Engineering Institute, Dimičeva ulica 12, 1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia

² University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Chemistry and Chemical Technology, Večna pot 113, 1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia

³ Faculty of Polymer Technology, Ozare 19, 2380 Slovenj Gradec, Slovenia

⁴ Institute of Environmental Technology, CEET, VŠB-Technical University of Ostrava, 17. listopadu 2172/15, Ostrava-Poruba 708 00, Czech Republic

* Corresponding author: Peter Nadrah, E-mail: peter.nadrah@zag.si

Abstract

TiO₂-CeO₂ composites have emerged as efficient photocatalysts compared to individual oxides. To elucidate the influence of Ce:Ti ratio and synthesis approach on photocatalytic performance, we synthesised mesoporous TiO₂-CeO₂ composites via evaporation-induced self-assembly (EISA) method with Ce:Ti ratio in the range of 0-20 mol%. Two synthesis approaches were employed: (1) incorporation of separately-synthesised CeO₂ during TiO₂ formation and (2) physical mixing of separately-synthesised TiO₂ and CeO₂. The materials exhibited type IV N₂ sorption isotherms, moderate specific surface area (up to 150 m²·g⁻¹) and pore sizes in the 3-15 nm range. The dominant crystalline phase was anatase with cerianite detected at higher Ce:Ti ratios (5 and 20 mol%). In photocatalytic CO₂ reduction to CH₄ and CO several TiO₂-CeO₂ composites outperformed pure TiO₂ and P25 under selected conditions. The physical mixture of TiO₂ and CeO₂ with 1 mol% Ce:Ti ratio demonstrated superior CH₄ production at low CO₂ concentrations (pH 12.9), while the TiO₂ with incorporated CeO₂ at 5 mol% Ce:Ti ratio excelled at higher CO₂ concentrations (pH 7), exhibiting higher absolute CH₄ production and improved selectivity compared to P25. Additionally, several TiO₂-CeO₂ composites showed enhanced CO production highlighting the potential of these materials for efficient CH₄ and CO generation from CO₂ photoreduction. These findings underscore the importance of optimizing cerium content and synthesis strategies to maximize the photocatalytic efficiency of TiO₂-based composites.

Keywords: TiO₂-CeO₂, evaporation-induced self-assembly, photocatalysis, mesoporous materials, CO₂ reduction

Introduction

Photocatalytic materials can be used to harness the energy from sunlight to drive the desired chemical reactions. Currently, much of the research is focused on the production of energy-rich compounds: reduction of CO₂ to energy-rich hydrocarbons or to CO (as a part of reforming gas) and to water splitting into produce hydrogen and oxygen^[1]. The benefit of using CO₂ as a reactant is two-fold: it decreases CO₂ concentration and produces energy-rich compounds that can be further used in place of fossil fuels. TiO₂ is a well-known photocatalyst and exhibits high photocatalytic activity. However, TiO₂ alone has several limitations, such as a high recombination rate of photogenerated electrons and oxygen vacancies and low absorption of visible portion of the sunlight^[2]. Synthesis of TiO₂ with different crystalline phases, doping and the introduction of other photocatalysts^[3] and cocatalysts^[1,4] can mitigate these shortcomings. TiO₂-CeO₂ composites have been reported to have increased visible light absorption and photocatalytic activity compared to pure TiO₂^[5-7]. Cerium in CeO₂ can shift between the Ce³⁺ and Ce⁴⁺ oxidation states^[6]. This unique property makes cerium oxide (commonly referred to as CeO₂, despite the presence of Ce³⁺ state) attractive for catalytic and renewable energy applications^[8].

Mesoporous materials (pore size: 2-50 nm according to IUPAC) have a much larger specific surface area compared to non-porous materials and therefore possess a larger surface area for the photocatalytic reactions. Sol-gel method is a well-known procedure to synthesise mesoporous oxides using soft templating methods (e.g., surfactants). Evaporation-induced self-assembly (EISA) method^[9] of synthesis offers an alternative to the classical sol-gel synthesis. In EISA, a reaction mixture is placed in a chamber with constant temperature and relative humidity to evaporate the volatile compounds, while hydrolysis and subsequent condensation (in the case of metal alkoxides as precursors) produce a gel-like material. The use of structure-directing agents, such as polypropylene polyethylene copolymers (e.g., Pluronic), leads to the formation of micelles and condensation of metal precursors to inorganic matrix surrounding the micelles to achieve mesoporous structure^[10-12]. The method is well-suited for the synthesis of TiO₂ from titanium alkoxides, which have higher reactivity compared to silicon alkoxides. EISA was recently used to prepare mesoporous TiO₂ with a well-ordered hexagonal (*P6mm*) pore arrangement^[13], which is difficult to achieve for TiO₂. CeO₂ can be synthesized from cerium salts and then used in further synthesis, for example in sol-gel synthesis of TiO₂-CeO₂ from titanium alkoxides^[14-16] or in a physical mixture with separately-synthesised TiO₂^[5,17]. CeO₂-TiO₂ materials were reported for photocatalytic CO₂ reduction^[18-21] and for degradation of organic compounds^[22-25]. Mesoporous materials still present a small portion of the materials in these reports. TiO₂-CeO₂ composites have other properties with potential uses as well, such as antimicrobial activity^[26] for potential use in wound healing^[27].

To the best of our knowledge, there have been no reports on the influence of Ce:Ti ratio on the synthesis of mesoporous TiO₂-CeO₂ using EISA method for photocatalytic CO₂ reduction applications. Given the benefits of CeO₂-TiO₂ composites, understanding the influence of

Ce:Ti ratio would facilitate tailoring of the products, particularly increasing the photocatalytic activity.

Herein, we report on the TiO₂-CeO₂ composites synthesized using two different approaches: the introduction of separately-synthesized CeO₂ into the reaction mixture during TiO₂ synthesis (approach 1) and the physical mixture of the separately-synthesized CeO₂ and TiO₂ (approach 2). We compared the influence of the synthesis approach and Ce:Ti ratio on the properties and photocatalytic activity of the products.

Experimental

Chemicals

The following chemicals were used in the experiments: titanium butoxide (TBOT) (Merck Sigma-Aldrich), cerium nitrate hexahydrate (Aldrich), Pluronic F127 (Sigma), 36 % hydrochloric acid (Merck Supelco), acetic acid (Honeywell Fluka), HPLC grade water (Honeywell Riedel-de Haën) and ethanol (Honeywell Riedel-de Haën).

Syntheses

TiO₂-CeO₂ composites were synthesized following two different approaches with four different amounts of cerium species. Pure CeO₂ and pure TiO₂ were synthesised separately.

TiO₂ synthesis in the presence of CeO₂ (TCO samples) - approach 1

TiO₂-CeO₂ composites were synthesized with a sol-gel reaction using EISA method in controlled conditions at 40 °C and 33 % RH, followed by calcination. The synthesis consisted of three main steps. Separately-synthesized CeO₂ was used in four different amounts: 0.2, 1, 5 and 20 mol% as Ce:Ti ratio. CeO₂ (0.002, 0.01, 0.05 or 0.2 equiv. of cerium) was added to ethanol (34 mL), followed by 36 % hydrochloric acid (2.5 mL), acetic acid (1.68 mL), water (0.8 mL up total 10 equiv.) and Pluronic F127 (1.85 g) in 100 mL round bottom flask and then heated at 40 °C for 1 hour during stirring. Afterwards, titanium(IV) butoxide (5 mL, 1 equiv.) was slowly added to the dispersion containing CeO₂ and stirred for 1 hour at 40 °C. The reaction mixture was then transferred to petri dishes and placed in a chamber with controlled conditions of 40 °C and 33 % RH for 24 hours to evaporate the volatile compounds. Afterwards, the obtained gel was calcined for 4 hours at 400 °C with a heating ramp 1 K/min. Finally, the material was crushed for 10 minutes in an agate mortar.

Physical mixtures of TiO₂ and CeO₂ (PM samples) - approach 2

First, pure TiO₂ and pure CeO₂ were separately-synthesized using EISA method, followed by calcination. Pure TiO₂ (1 equiv. of titanium) and pure CeO₂ (0.002, 0.01, 0.05 or 0.2 equiv. of cerium) were mixed and crushed in agate mortar for 10 min. Then, the physical mixture was calcined for 4 hours at 400 °C with a ramp 1 K/min. After calcination, the sample was crushed again in an agate mortar for 10 min.

Pure TiO₂ synthesis

Pure TiO₂ (label TCO-0) was synthesized according to the approach 1 but without the CeO₂. Pure TiO₂ as a reference for PM samples was thermally treated twice (label PM-0).

Pure CeO₂ synthesis

Pure CeO₂ was synthesized with a sol-gel reaction using EISA method in controlled conditions at 40 °C and 33 % relative humidity (RH), followed by calcination. The synthesis consisted of three main steps. 1 equiv. (6.383 g) of cerium nitrate hexahydrate was added to ethanol (34 mL), followed by water (2.65 mL, 10 equiv.) and Pluronic F127 (1.85 g) in 100 mL round bottom flask and then heated at 40 °C for 1 hour while stirring. The reaction mixture was then transferred to petri dishes and placed in a chamber with controlled conditions of 40 °C and 33 % RH for 24 hours to evaporate the volatile compounds. Afterwards, the obtained gel was calcined for 4 hours at 400 °C with a heating ramp of 1 K/min. Finally, the material was crushed for 10 minutes in an agate mortar to yield the product (label CeO₂*). A portion of it was thermally treated for the second time (label CeO₂**).

Characterisation

X-ray powder diffraction (XRD)

XRD analyses were done on PANalytical X'Pert PRO with Cu K α radiation at 45 kV and 40 mA. The diffractograms were recorded in 20-90° 2 θ range with 0.033° 2 θ step size and 100 s virtual time. 0.02 rad Soller slit, a 10 mm mask and an automatic divergence slit were used on the incident beam side. An automatic anti-scattering slit and 0.02 rad Soller slit were used on the diffracted beam side. The ratio of crystalline phases was calculated with Rietveld refinement. Crystallite sizes were calculated using Scherrer equation from non-overlapping reflections of anatase and cerianite using full width half maximum (FWHM) values.

Nitrogen sorption

Nitrogen sorption isotherms were recorded on Micromeritics ASAP 2020 instrument at 77 K. Specific surface area was calculated using Brunauer-Emmet-Teller (BET) model. Pore width was calculated with Barrett-Joyner-Halenda (BJH) model using Halsey thickness curve and standard BJH correction.

Photocatalytic reduction of CO₂ and H₂O

Photocatalytic tests were conducted in a batch-mixed photoreactor made of stainless steel with a volume of 357 mL. The reaction mixture consisted of 100 mL of 0.2 M NaOH and the tested photocatalyst (0.1 g), and was saturated with either helium (pH = 12.9) or CO₂ (pH = 7) to remove air and saturate the solution. An 8 W Hg UVC lamp ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 254 \text{ nm}$; Ultra-Violet Products Inc.) served as the light source and was positioned horizontally on a quartz glass window at the top of the photoreactor. The reactor was securely sealed, and prior to initiating the reaction (by turning on the lamp), a gas sample was drawn at time 0 h through a septum using a syringe. The gas samples were analysed using a gas chromatograph (Shimadzu Nexis GC-2030) equipped with a barrier discharge ionization detector (BID). The reaction mixture was irradiated over specific time intervals (0-8 h), with samples collected

after 2, 4, 6, and 8 hours for analysis. The photocatalytic reduction of CO₂ and H₂O yielded three detectable products: hydrogen, methane, and carbon monoxide. The stability of the tested sample was confirmed by repeatedly using the same batch, yielding reproducible results.

Results and discussion

We synthesized TiO₂-CeO₂ using EISA method following two approaches: (1) synthesis of TiO₂ in the presence of separately-synthesized CeO₂ (sample label TCO) and (2) physical mixing separately-synthesized TiO₂ and CeO₂ (sample label PM) as summarized in Table 1. Pure TiO₂ and CeO₂ were synthesized separately using titanium butoxide and cerium nitrate, respectively. All TCO samples were thermally treated (calcined) once, while the PM samples were thermally treated (calcined) twice: the first time after the synthesis of the individual oxides and the second time after physical mixing. Pure CeO₂ is labelled CeO₂* and CeO₂** for the sample thermally treated once and twice, respectively.

Table 1. List of synthesized TiO₂-CeO₂ materials with their labels. Samples TCO-0 and PM-0 refer to pure TiO₂ without CeO₂ component, calcined once and twice, respectively.

Approach		Percentile of Ce:Ti molar ratio (mol%)				
		0	0.2	1	5	20
1	Synthesis of TiO ₂ in the presence of CeO ₂	TCO-0	TCO-0.2	TCO-1	TCO-5	TCO-20
2	Physically mixing TiO ₂ and CeO ₂	PM-0	PM-0.2	PM-1	PM-5	PM-20

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) of the selected TiO₂-CeO₂ materials revealed agglomerates without clear boundaries as depicted in Figure 1C and D, morphologically similar to pure TiO₂ (Figure 1A). In the case of CeO₂*, particles of approx. 100 nm and smaller can be observed in Figure 1B. In the case of TCO-5 and PM-5 it is possible to identify areas with CeO₂ particles (Figure 1C and D), however, this cannot be confirmed based solely on the morphology. The materials were in the form of a self-standing film (1-2 mm thick), thus a product in the form of an interconnected network is expected.

Figure 1. FE-SEM micrographs of the selected samples: (A) TCO-0 (pure TiO_2), (B) CeO_2^* , (C) TCO-5 and (D) PM-5.

The crystalline phase ratios calculated using Rietveld refinement of diffractograms are depicted in Figure 2, while full diffractograms are available in Supporting information (Figure S1). Crystalline phases for all samples comprised predominantly anatase (ICDD No. 21-1272) and a small amount of rutile (ICDD No. 21-1276). Crystalline CeO_2 (cerianite, ICDD No. 04-007-8802) can be detected only in the samples with 1 mol% (in traces), 5 mol% and 20 mol% Ce:Ti ratio and follows well the increasing ratio. Diffractograms of samples with a higher Ce:Ti ratio (especially 20 mol%) exhibit anatase reflections of lower intensity not only due to lower anatase content but presumably due to lower crystallinity.

Figure 2. Phase ratios of the crystalline phases of $\text{TiO}_2\text{-CeO}_2$ composites determined by XRD. The numbers on the x-axis refer to Ce:Ti molar percentile ratio (mol%).

The crystallite sizes of anatase calculated using Scherrer equation are presented in the Figure 3. Anatase crystallite sizes fall roughly into 8-9 nm range for all samples, while cerianite sizes are much larger on the order of several tens of nanometres. Anatase size does not change much with increasing Ce content. We postulate based on the results of TCO that the presence of CeO_2 particles during EISA and thermal treatment does not hinder the formation of anatase crystals.

Figure 3. Crystallite sizes of anatase (left axis) and cerianite (right axis) of the $\text{TiO}_2\text{-CeO}_2$ composites. Cerianite size for samples below 5 mol% Ce:Ti ratio could not be determined. CeO_2^* and CeO_2^{**} refer to the separately-synthesized CeO_2 , thermally treated once and twice, respectively. The numbers on the x-axis refer to Ce:Ti molar percentile ratio (mol%).

The mesoporous structure of the samples was determined with nitrogen sorption. The isotherms (Figure 4A and B) are of the type IV according to IUPAC with hysteresis loops of the type H1 and H2. Distribution of pore diameters (Figure 4C and D) show predominantly

pores in the 3-15 nm range. A decrease of peak height can be observed in the samples with increasing CeO₂ content. The materials exhibit moderate S_{BET} (80-150 m²·g⁻¹) and an increase of S_{BET} only from Ce:Ti ratio 0.2 to 1 mol% and then a decrease with increasing percentage of Ce as presented in Figure 5. Pore volume shows the same trend of a decrease with increasing Ce:Ti ratio but with a different order for lower Ce:Ti ratios (0.2-5 mol%) and falls into 0.20-0.35 cm³·g⁻¹ range as presented in Figure 5. Both TCO-0.2 and PM-0.2 do not follow this sequence and exhibit lower S_{BET} and pore volume compared to the expected value according to the sequence above. Pure CeO₂ has relatively low S_{BET} (14 m²·g⁻¹) and pore volume (0.04 cm³·g⁻¹). Very low S_{BET} and porosity of the CeO₂ used for the synthesis is presumably responsible for the decrease of S_{BET} as the Ce:Ti ratio increases, particularly in the case of 1, 5 and 20 mol% Ce:Ti ratios. Slightly smaller crystallite sizes (~1 nm differences for anatase particles (Figure 3)) and higher S_{BET} for TCO compared to PM samples for the same Ce:Ti ratio correspond well with differences between TCO-0 and PM-0 (pure TiO₂ calcined once and twice, respectively) and can be ascribed to two thermal treatments for PM samples.

Figure 4. Nitrogen sorption isotherms for TCO (A) and PM (B) samples and pore size distribution determined from the adsorption curve for TCO (C) and PM (D) samples. The curves are offset on the y-axes by $60 \text{ cm}^3 \cdot \text{g}^{-1} \text{ STP}$ and $0.015 \text{ cm}^3 \cdot \text{g}^{-1} \cdot \text{nm}^{-1}$ for A, B and C, D, respectively.

Figure 5. Specific surface area determined by BET (left axis) and pore volume (right axis) of the synthesized TiO₂-CeO₂ composites. Pore volume is calculated from adsorption isotherm at $p/p^\circ = 0.99$. The numbers on the x-axis refer to Ce:Ti molar percentile ratio (mol%).

We performed diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (DRS) to analyse the spectroscopic characteristics of the materials. The reflectance spectra of pure TiO₂ show high reflectance above 410 nm and a steep decrease below 400 nm as expected for anatase (Figures S2 and S3). CeO₂^{*}, on the other hand, exhibits a decrease at approx. 450 nm and below, which is in line with known higher absorption of visible light by CeO₂^{*} compared to crystalline TiO₂. A decrease of reflectance in 400-500 nm range is not observed in the samples. Since CeO₂ is already formed before it is added to TiO₂, we can reason that doping with cerium, which could affect light absorption^[28], did not occur.

The photocatalytic activity was evaluated for photocatalytic reduction of CO₂ and H₂ production at two different pH levels: 12.9, corresponding to a low concentration of dissolved CO₂ (84 mg·dm⁻³) and 7, corresponding to a high concentration of dissolved CO₂ (9744 mg·dm⁻³). As depicted in Figure 6A and D, H₂ production was the highest for pure TiO₂ (TCO-0), only slightly lower than the reference TiO₂ P25. PM-1 sample exhibited the second highest activity at pH 12.9 (Figure 6A), but significantly lower at pH = 7 (Figure 6D). Both TCO-0 and PM-1 excelled in CH₄ production at pH = 12.9, with PM-1 having slightly higher activity compared to TCO-0 (Figure 6B). Interestingly, at pH = 7, TCO-5 exhibited the highest CH₄ production, even surpassing P25 (Figure 6E). CO production at pH = 12.9 was robust across all samples, with all but PM-0.2 surpassing P25 (Figure 6C). At pH = 7, CO production was significantly higher than at pH 12.9, and once again, all samples except one (PM-1) exceeded the CO production of P25 (Figure 6F). This analysis highlights the strong influence of the pH on the photocatalytic performance of the TiO₂-CeO₂ composites. High CH₄ production can be achieved even at a lower amount of available CO₂ (pH = 12.9).

Figure 6. Yield of hydrogen (A, D), methane (B, E) and carbon monoxide (C, F) during photocatalytic reduction of CO₂ at pH = 12.9 (A-C) and pH = 7 (D-F) after 8 hours with selected TCO and PM samples and P25 as a reference. The numbers on the x-axis refer to Ce:Ti molar percentile ratio (mol%). Note: scales of y-axes are the same in each column for easier comparison, but differ in each row.

The graphs in Figure 7 offer detailed insights into the selectivity of the photocatalytic reduction of CO₂ and proportional yields of the photocatalytic products (H₂, CH₄, and CO) based on the Ce ratio and the synthesis approach (TCO vs. PM). The selectivity for CO₂ reduction to CH₄ and CO S_{CO_2} describes the competitive reactions of CO₂ reduction and H₂O reduction. The selectivity is calculated according to the following equation, if the main CO₂ reduction products are CH₄ and CO, and the main H₂O reduction product is H₂:

$$S_{CO_2} = \frac{2R_{CO} + 8R_{CH_4}}{2R_{CO} + 8R_{CH_4} + 2R_{H_2}} \times 100 \%$$

where R is the production rate of each product and the coefficient preceding R is the number of electrons consumed to yield each particular product. At pH 12.9, where the concentration of dissolved CO₂ is lower, distinct trends in selectivity and product yields were observed among the different samples (Figure 7A). The TCO-0 sample (pure TiO₂) exhibited a high proportion of H₂ (81 %) and a cumulative CO and CH₄ product proportion of 19 % (with 17 % CH₄ and 2 % CO), leading to S_{CO_2} of 46 %. As the cerium content increased, the

selectivity towards CO₂ reduction improved. Specifically, the TCO-5 sample demonstrated a significant enhancement in selectivity, with a cumulative CO and CH₄ product proportion of 32 % (24 % CH₄ and 8 % CO), and S_{CO_2} of 60 %. This indicates that the presence of CeO₂ in this sample enhances selectivity towards CO₂ reduction. The PM-5 sample showed the most notable performance with the highest CH₄ yield proportion (52 %) and S_{CO_2} of 89 %, significantly surpassing the P25 reference, which had a CO yield proportion of only 1 %, a CH₄ proportion of 19 % and S_{CO_2} of 49 %. These results suggest that the physical mixing method, particularly at a Ce:Ti ratio of 5mol%, is highly effective in enhancing CO and CH₄ production at higher pH level. At pH 7, where the concentration of dissolved CO₂ is higher, the photocatalytic behaviour exhibited notable differences (Figure 7B). The TCO-0 sample maintained a high H₂ yield (85 %) and a CH₄ proportion of 9 %, leading to S_{CO_2} of 33 %. The TCO-5 sample continued to show improved selectivity for CO₂ reduction, achieving a cumulative CO and CH₄ product proportion of 44 %, with a CH₄ proportion of 27 %, making it the most effective composite for CO₂ reduction at this pH with selectivity of 69 %. The PM-5 sample exhibited a lower CH₄ proportion (8 %) but a higher CO proportion of 18 %, resulting in S_{CO_2} of 40 %. This indicates that while the physical mixing method remains effective, its performance slightly diminishes at lower pH compared to higher pH. CO₂ selectivity at pH 7 was comparable among all tested PM samples and showed less variation compared to pH 12.9. The P25 reference sample showed lower selectivity at both pH levels, with S_{CO_2} of 33 % at pH 7 and 49 % at pH 12.9. This confirms that the mesoporous TiO₂-CeO₂ composites synthesized using the approach 1 (TCO) and approach 2 (PM) offer superior photocatalytic performance for CO₂ reduction compared to pure TiO₂. The results demonstrate that both the Ce ratio and the synthesis approach significantly influence the photocatalytic efficiency and selectivity of TiO₂-CeO₂ composites. The two samples with a Ce:Ti ratio of 5 mol% exhibited high selectivity at both pH levels and achieved the highest yield for CH₄ production at pH 7. Additionally, the PM-5 sample showed remarkable performance, particularly at pH 12.9, highlighting the potential of the physical mixing approach for optimizing photocatalytic properties. These findings underscore the importance of carefully tuning CeO₂ content and synthesis strategy to enhance the efficiency of TiO₂-based photocatalysts for sustainable CO₂ reduction.

Figure 7. The ratio of the yield of hydrogen, methane and carbon monoxide and selectivity during photocatalytic reduction of CO₂ at pH = 12.9 (A) and pH = 7 (B) after 8 hours with selected TCO and PM samples and P25 as a reference. The numbers on the x-axis refer to Ce:Ti molar percentile ratio (mol%).

Conclusions

We have successfully synthesised eight mesoporous TiO₂-CeO₂ composites following two approaches: (1) incorporation of CeO₂ during TiO₂ synthesis (TCO samples) and (2) physically mixing separately-synthesised TiO₂ and CeO₂ (PM samples) with Ce:Ti molar ratios in the range from 0 to 20 mol%. The resulting materials predominantly consisted of anatase and also cerianite at higher Ce:Ti ratios. They exhibited type IV isotherms with high specific surface area (up to 150 m²·g⁻¹) and pore sizes in the 3-15 nm range. We observed that increasing Ce:Ti ratio led to a decrease in the specific surface area and a reduction in the structural order of the mesoporous structures. Photocatalytic experiments showed that pure TiO₂ (TCO-0) performed exceptionally well in H₂ production, often closely matching or slightly underperforming the commercial TiO₂ reference (P25). Certain TiO₂-CeO₂ composites demonstrated superior performance under specific conditions. The PM-1 sample excelled in CH₄ production at low CO₂ concentrations (pH = 12.9), while the TCO-5 sample outperformed others at high CO₂ concentrations (pH = 7), showcasing its effectiveness in methane production under these conditions. Additionally, PM-5 exhibited the highest selectivity to products of photocatalytic CO₂ reduction, surpassing that of P25, along with improved CO production, indicating the beneficial effects of CeO₂ incorporation. These findings suggest that mesoporous TiO₂-CeO₂ composites synthesized via the EISA method hold significant potential for efficient CH₄ and CO production from photocatalytic CO₂ reduction. The performance of the TCO-5 and PM-1 samples, in particular, highlights the importance of optimizing Ce content and synthesis strategies to tailor TiO₂-based photocatalysts for enhanced selectivity and efficiency in CO₂ photoreduction applications.

CRedit author statement

Mateja Knap: Conceptualization, Investigation, Writing - Original Draft, Visualization; Urška Lavrenčič Štangar: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Writing - Review & Editing;

Andrijana Sever Škapin: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Writing - Review & Editing; Miroslava Filip Edelmannová: Investigation, Validation, Writing - Review & Editing. Kamila Kočí: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Writing - Review & Editing; Peter Nadrah: Conceptualization, Investigation, Validation, Supervision, Writing - Review & Editing.

Acknowledgements

We thank Edi Kranjc for the XRD measurements. The authors acknowledge the financial support by the Slovenian Research and Innovation Agency (Grants no. N2-0188, J2-4441, P2-0273 and P1-0134) and Czech Science Foundation (project No. GA CR 21–24268K).

Supporting information

Supplementary data to this article can be found in a separate document.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data availability

Raw data are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13740585>.

References

- [1] C. Xia, T. Hong Chuong Nguyen, X. Cuong Nguyen, S. Young Kim, D. L. T. Nguyen, P. Raizada, P. Singh, V.-H. Nguyen, C. Chien Nguyen, V. Chinh Hoang, Q. Van Le, *Fuel* **2022**, *307*, 121745.
- [2] Y. Wang, J. Zhao, T. Wang, Y. Li, X. Li, J. Yin, C. Wang, *Journal of Catalysis* **2016**, *337*, 293–302.
- [3] A. V. Emeline, A. V. Rudakova, V. K. Ryabchuk, N. Serpone, *Current Opinion in Green and Sustainable Chemistry* **2022**, 100588.
- [4] N. Rozman, P. Nadrah, R. Cornut, B. Joussetme, M. Bele, G. Dražić, M. Gaberšček, Š. Kunej, A. S. Škapin, *Int J Hydrogen Energ* **2021**, *46*, 32871–32881.
- [5] I. A. Mejia-Estrella, A. Pérez Larios, B. Sulbarán-Rangel, C. A. Guzmán González, *Materials* **2022**, *15*, 6784.
- [6] X. Gao, Y. Jiang, Y. Zhong, Z. Luo, K. Cen, *Journal of Hazardous Materials* **2010**, *174*, 734–739.
- [7] S. Pavasupree, Y. Suzuki, S. Pivsa-Art, S. Yoshikawa, *Journal of Solid State Chemistry* **2005**, *178*, 128–134.
- [8] N. A. Piro, J. R. Robinson, P. J. Walsh, E. J. Schelter, *Coordination Chemistry Reviews* **2014**, *260*, 21–36.
- [9] L. Mahoney, R. T. Koodali, *Materials* **2014**, *7*, 2697–2746.
- [10] L. Chen, B. Yao, Y. Cao, K. Fan, *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2007**, *111*, 11849–11853.
- [11] J. H. Pan, W. I. Lee, *Chem. Mater.* **2006**, *18*, 847–853.
- [12] J. H. Pan, X. S. Zhao, W. I. Lee, *Chemical Engineering Journal* **2011**, *170*, 363–380.
- [13] K. Lan, L. Liu, J. Yu, Y. Ma, J.-Y. Zhang, Z. Lv, S. Yin, Q. Wei, D. Zhao, *JACS Au* **2023**, *3*, 1141–1150.

- [14] Y. Zhu, G. Li, S. Zhang, J. Song, C. Mao, H. Niu, B. Jin, Y. Tian, *Electrochimica Acta* **2011**, *56*, 7550–7554.
- [15] C. Karunakaran, P. Navamani, P. Gomathisankar, *J IRAN CHEM SOC* **2015**, *12*, 75–80.
- [16] Y. Li, W. Li, F. Liu, M. Li, X. Qi, M. Xue, Y. Wang, F. Han, *J Nanopart Res* **2020**, *22*, 122.
- [17] Z. Zhu, D. He, *Fuel* **2008**, *87*, 2229–2235.
- [18] M. Liu, G. Jiang, Z. Zhao, Y. Shi, S. Zhao, *Dalton Trans.* **2024**, *53*, 17963–17975.
- [19] T. Wang, L. Chen, C. Chen, M. Huang, Y. Huang, S. Liu, B. Li, *ACS Nano* **2022**, *16*, 2306–2318.
- [20] P. Seeharaj, N. Vittayakorn, J. Morris, P. Kim-Lohsoontorn, *Nanotechnology* **2021**, *32*, 375707.
- [21] Y. Wang, B. Li, C. Zhang, L. Cui, S. Kang, X. Li, L. Zhou, *Applied Catalysis B: Environmental* **2013**, *130–131*, 277–284.
- [22] G. Li, D. Zhang, J. C. Yu, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2009**, *11*, 3775–3782.
- [23] M. Li, S. Zhang, L. Lv, M. Wang, W. Zhang, B. Pan, *Chemical Engineering Journal* **2013**, *229*, 118–125.
- [24] X. Wang, H. Xu, X. Luo, M. Li, M. Dai, Q. Chen, H. Song, *Colloid and Interface Science Communications* **2021**, *44*, 100476.
- [25] B. Palanisamy, C. M. Babu, B. Sundaravel, S. Anandan, V. Murugesan, *Journal of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology* **2013**, *13*, 2573–2581.
- [26] I. García-Casas, D. Valor, D. M. de los Santos, C. Pereyra, A. Montes, *Journal of CO2 Utilization* **2024**, *80*, 102667.
- [27] A. Sanmugam, L. K. Sellappan, S. Manoharan, A. Rameshkumar, R. S. Kumar, A. I. Almansour, N. Arumugam, H.-S. Kim, D. Vikraman, *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules* **2024**, *256*, 128458.
- [28] Z. Liu, L. Xing, H. Ma, L. Cheng, J. Liu, J. Yang, Q. Zhang, *Environmental Progress & Sustainable Energy* **2017**, *36*, 494–504.